

Effect of intermediate strain rates on shear plugging strength of composites

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Experimental determination of shear strength of GFRP and CFRP woven composite laminates

- E-glass/epoxy and Carbon/epoxy laminates were prepared using VARTM technique.
- Composites made with 12 layers fabric each with 200 GSM aerial density.
- LY556 epoxy mixed with HY951 hardener in 10:0.9 ratio.
- Shear punching test performed in UTM according to ASTM D732-02.
- Strain rates varied by changing UTM cross head speed from 1 to 500 mm per minute.
- Shear strength calculated as $\tau_{SP} = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi dt}$.
- Strain rate defined as the ratio of cross head speed to clearance.

Fig 1- Assembled and section view of the fixture and specimen

Shear plugged specimen

Fig 2 - Image of the shear plugged composite specimens: (a) E-glass/epoxy specimen (b) Carbon/epoxy specimen

Comparison of shear plugging strengths

Fig 3 – Comparison of shear strength of E-glass/epoxy and Carbon/epoxy laminate as a function of strain rate.

Results and conclusion

- Shear plugging strength of FRP composite laminates has been found.
- Increase in strain rate causes increase in strength for GFRP laminate.
- Strain rate increment from 0.17 to 83.33 s⁻¹ resulted in 35.3% strength increment.
- CFRP laminate seemed insensitive to strain rate.
- Rate sensitivity decreased with increase in strain rate.

Strain rate (s ⁻¹)	Glass/epoxy (MPa)	Carbon/epoxy (MPa)
0.17	107.6	184.55
8.33	119.8	182.5
16.67	130.5	178.95
33.33	139.0	186.42
83.33	145.6	180.75

Table 1- Comparison of shear strengths